

Impact of Alumina and Silicon Carbide Fillers on Epoxy/Glass Fiber Based Hybrid Composites' Dimensional Stability

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Abstract:

Background: This study investigates the effects of alumina and silicon carbide additives on the physical behavior of epoxy/glass fiber hybrid polymer composites. The introduction of these fillers at various concentrations aims to assess their influence on composite properties, crucial for applications requiring enhanced mechanical strength and moisture resistance.

Method: Utilizing a systematic experimental approach, the research assesses the density, moisture content, water absorption, and linear swelling behaviors of composites formulated with varying concentrations of aluminium oxide and silicon carbide (0, 2, 4, and 6 wt.%).

Results: The results indicate that composites without any fillers exhibit the highest density (2.708 g/cm³) and water absorption (1.5%), attributed to optimal resin-fiber bonding and poor compatibility between the matrix and fibers, respectively. Introduction of 2 wt. % filler reduces water absorption to 0.672% and decreases linear swelling due to the hydrophobic properties of silicon carbide. Conversely, increasing the filler content to 6 wt. % enhances moisture content, water absorption, and linear swelling, particularly due to the hydrophilic nature of aluminium oxide, impacting dimensional stability negatively.

Conclusion: This research highlights the critical balance between filler content and composite properties, emphasizing the role of particulate type in influencing the performance characteristics of epoxy-based composites. These insights provide a foundation for designing fiber-reinforced composites tailored for specific industrial applications.

Keywords: Alumina, Epoxy, Glass fiber, Physical property, Silicon carbide

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1. Introduction

High-strength fibers like boron, carbon, glass, and aramid are embedded into polymer resins like vinyl ester, epoxy, and polyester to create fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs). The combination results in a material that benefits from the resin's durability and the fibers' strength, yielding superior properties unattainable by the individual components. FRPs offer high modulus and strength, with thermoplastic polymer-based composites exhibiting higher storage and loss modulus and elevated glass transition temperatures. Epoxy resins, noted for their corrosion and chemical resistance, low shrinkage, and versatile processing, serve as matrices and structural adhesives. Incorporating alumina and silicon carbide further enhances the physical and mechanical properties, including tensile strength, impact strength, thermal expansion, and hardness [1-6]. [7] examined sugar palm fiber (SPF) reinforced thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) composites, finding that dimensional stability and density improved with increasing SPF content, reaching optimal values at 50 wt.% SPF over 168 hours. Higher SPF concentration in plasticized sugar palm starch (SPS) bio-composites reduced water absorption and moisture content

while improving mechanical qualities up to 30 weight percent SPF, according to [8]. [9] Also studied SPF and glass fiber (GF) reinforced polyurethane composites, observing that water uptake and thickness swelling increased with SPF/GF content (30/10). At the same time, density, impact strength, flexural strength, and modulus improved with increased glass fiber reinforcement (maximum at SPF/GF-0/40). [10] Evaluated bamboo fiber-reinforced polyurethane composites, noting that bamboo fibers had lower moisture content, density, and swelling percentage than flax, and jute fibers. [11] Studied thermoplastic starch (TPS) composites reinforced with eggshell powder (EP) and commercial calcium carbonate (CC). They found that TPS/EP composites had better water absorption resistance and lower weight loss after soil burial degradation than TPS/CC and plain TPS composites. [12] Investigated jute fiber-reinforced epoxy composites, finding that increasing jute fiber content reduced void fraction and improved hardness, tensile, and impact strength, with optimal properties at 48 wt% jute fiber. However, flexural strength decreased due to void content. Similarly, [13] observed that increasing jute fiber content in oil palm EFB fiber and jute fiber hybrid epoxy composites increased density and chemical resistance while decreasing void content, thickness swelling, and water uptake. [14] Explored the influences of fly ash filler in polyester-based E-glass fiber composites. They found that composites with up to 10 wt. % fly ash exhibited excellent mechanical properties, while higher fly ash content decreased these properties. In a related study, [15] reported that polyester-based E-glass fiber

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composites without filler showed optimal mechanical properties up to 30 wt. % fiber content. [16] Investigated hybrid composites of coconut coir fiber and glass fiber reinforced with epoxy, observing increased moisture absorption with more coconut coir fiber and improved flexural and impact strength with higher fiber content. [17] Studied coconut fiber (CCF) reinforced cassava starch-based bio-composites, finding that increased CCF content reduced dimensional stability and moisture absorption, with mechanical properties peaking at 30 wt.% CCF. [18] examined pinus radiata sawdust (PRW) reinforced recycled thermoplastics (RTP) composites, finding that moisture absorption and thickness swelling decreased with five wt% MAPP, and the composite with 45 wt.% PP, 50 wt.% PRW, and 5 wt.% MAPP exhibited the best dimensional stability. A study by [19] examined the density and properties of water absorption of epoxy composites reinforced with woven flax/glass fibers. The study revealed densities ranging from 1.26 to 1.31 g/cc. Water absorption tests showed that dedicated flax composites had the highest absorption rate at 9.86%, whereas glass/epoxy composites exhibited the lowest at 1.51%, indicating significant variability influenced by fiber composition. Recycled newspaper fiber (RNF) and poplar wood flour (PWF) reinforced recycled polypropylene (RPP) composites were studied by [20] and they found that composites with higher moisture absorption and thickness swelling had 0-2 wt. % MAPP, while six wt. % MAPP composites had lower values and better dimensional stability. Similarly, [21] reported that a 50:50 volume fraction of epoxy to glass fiber composite exhibited the best mechanical characteristics among the tested configurations. [22] Investigated epoxy-based E-glass fiber composites with fillers, noting that 10 wt. % magnesium hydroxide provided the highest tensile strength, 15 wt. % silicon carbide gave the best impact strength and hardness, and 10 wt. % silicon carbide yielded the best flexural strength.

Most of the Investigators investigated the density and dimension stability of fiber bio-composites only, in fact, no study has been found more than one particular filled with glass fiber reinforced composites. This article examined the effects on the physical behaviour and dimensional stability of glass-fiber-epoxy hybrid polymer composites of varying weight percentages of Al₂O₃ and SiC.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Matrix Material

The low-temperature curing epoxy resin LY 556 (Biphenyl-A-Diglycidyl-Ether, 1026 gm/cc at 25°C) and hardener HY951 (10:1 ratio by weight) as shown in figure 1 (a) were selected for this experimental work. Epoxy resin (LY556) and hardener (HY951) supplied by Savita Scientific and Plastic Products at 445, Mishra Rajai's street 1st cross Indira Bazaar Jaipur-302001. Epoxy resin (LY 556) and hardener (HY951) manufactured by ASES Chemical Works at industrial chemical division B-48-50, industrial estate, Jodhpur- 342003.

2.2 Fiber Material

The high chemical resistance, tensile strength, insulating properties, and inexpensive cost of glass fiber make it a popular choice for use in polymer matrix composites. E-glass fiber as shown in Figure 1 (b) is used for economical applications such small passenger aircraft, rocket motor casings etc., while S-glass fiber is utilized in fuselage skin, bullet proof glass etc. [23]. So, in this study, woven bi-directional E-glass fibers were used as the reinforcing material for all composites. These fibers are made from very fine glass strands. The properties of these fibers depend on their length, orientation, and volume fraction [4, 29]. The woven bi-directional E-glass fiber manufactured by Ciba Geigy and locally supplied by Savita Scientific and Plastic Products at 445, Mishra Rajai's Street 1st cross Indira Bazaar Jaipur-302001, is used as a reinforcing material in all the composites in the present work.

Table 1: Glass fiber chemical compositions expressed as a percentage of weight [24, 28]

Composition	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	B ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O
Wt. %	55	15	0.25	6.75	22	1.5	1.5

Figure 1: Materials (a) Epoxy and Hardener (b) E-Glass fiber (c) Al₂O₃ (d) SiC [5]

2.3 Additive Materials

For the current work, silicon carbide and aluminium oxide were chosen as fillers for their exceptional properties that ensure high performance. Carbon and silicon combine to form silicon carbide, a material with great thermal shock resistance, low density, high hardness, and chemical inertness up to 800 °C, all of which contribute to its superior performance. Aluminium oxide, with its high strength, wear resistance, dielectric properties, and stability at elevated temperatures in its hexagonal alpha phase, further enhances the quality of our material selection [25]. Silicon carbide powder of mesh size 1200 as shown in figure 1 (d) purchased

from ASES Chemical Works at industrial chemical division B-48-50, industrial estate, Jodhpur- 342003. Whereas Aluminium oxide active neutral (200 mesh) as shown in figure 1 (c), purchased from S D Fine- chemicals limited at 315-317, T.V. industrial estate, 243, worli road, Mumbai- 30.

2.4 Fabrication of Composites

For the fabrication of composites the concentration of glass fibers kept constant i.e. 40 wt. % serves several strategic reasons. It enables a clear comparison of multiple sample variants, isolating the influence of additional components such as epoxy and fillers (aluminium oxide and silicon carbide) on the composites' physical properties and dimensional stabilities. This standardisation assures that any observed changes in characteristics are directly related to the fillers and not to variances in fiber content. The chosen fiber fraction is most likely an ideal balance, either from past studies, to provide desirable physical behaviour and dimensional stability while simplifying manufacturing processes. The stacking method was selected for its simplicity and effectiveness in layering various materials to achieve uniform thickness and fiber distribution. Alternatives such as automated lay-up or resin infusion are certainly viable and offer advantages in terms of scale and reproducibility but require significantly more sophisticated equipment and setup. The manual stacking method allows for precise control over the placement of fibers and fillers, crucial for experimental research where small adjustments in

composition can have pronounced effects on the properties of the composite.

The method for preparing the composite involved several steps. First, ten wooden plates were cut to dimensions of 350 mm by 350 mm by 10 mm. Plastic sheets and glass fiber sheets were also cut to 320 mm by 320 mm by 1 mm and 300 mm by 300 mm by 1 mm, respectively. Wooden planks support and cure composites during manufacture. Plank dimensions affect composite panel uniformity and thickness, ensuring that each specimen meets precise testing criteria. Wood is chosen for its rigidity, flatness, and ease of handling during composite layup and curing. After that hardener and curing agent (HY951) were combined with epoxy resin in a 1:10 ratio. The composition included 40 wt.% woven E-glass fiber and varying concentrations of epoxy (60, 56, 52, and 48 wt.%), along with aluminium oxide and silicon carbide fillers at 0, 2, 4, and 6 wt.% as per table 2. This mixture was applied onto the E-glass fiber, followed by additional epoxy coatings, and a roller was used to remove air traps and excess polymer. The layering continued until the desired thickness was achieved. Before the top mould plate was pressed onto the stacked layers, a release gel was sprayed on it. The composite portion was removed from the mould once it had cured for 24 hours at room temperature. This procedure was repeated with different filler weight percentages to assess the physical behavior and dimensional stability [24, 30].

Table 2:Representation of developed hybrid polymer composites

Designation	Compositions (wt. %)				Specimen
	Epoxy	Glass fiber	Al ₂ O ₃	SiC	
P	60	40	0	0	
Q	56	40	2	2	
R	52	40	4	4	
S	48	40	6	6	

3. Experimental Work

3.1 Density, Moisture, Water Absorption and Thickness Swelling Test

Figure 2: Specimens of developed composites for density test

Figures 2 and 3 show the samples for density, moisture, water absorption and thickness swelling test respectively. All the specimens were prepared according to ASTM standards. Table 3 shows the parameters for physical characteristics and dimensional stability of developed hybrid polymer composites the buoyancy method, which entails weighing the specimen both in air and in liquid and computing the difference using Archimedes' principle, is used to estimate the density of specimens. Because fibers are sensitive to moisture and humidity, the moisture content test determines the water content in composites. This entails reweighing the specimens after drying to a constant mass at a given temperature.

To find the amount of water absorbed, specimens are dried, weighed, submerged in water for a day, and then weighed once more. To assess swelling, specimens are dried, their initial dimensions are measured, they are submerged in water for 24 hours, and then the measurements are taken again. These tests offer insightful information about the material characteristics of composites in a variety of settings [32, 33, 34]. All the experiments were conducted at RCERT Jaipur in June 2024.

4. Results and Discussions

The physical characteristics of woven E-glass fiber-reinforced epoxy composites vary significantly with changes in resin, filler, and particulate content. Table 4 represents the Physical properties and dimensional stability of developed composites for different periods Figure 4 shows the Comparison of density, moisture, absorption and linear swelling of developed composites. The density of these composites is primarily affected by the presence of fillers such as Al₂O₃ and SiC. A maximum density of 2.708 g/cm³ is observed in composites without particulate fillers, attributed to superior bonding and minimal void presence. Introducing a two wt.% combination of alumina and silicon carbide fillers slightly decreases the density to 2.651 g/cm³ due to air bubbles and incomplete fiber wetting during curing [7,13]. However, increasing the filler content from 2 to 6 wt.% raises the density to 2.662 g/cm³, owing to the denser nature of the particulates. Moisture content (MC) also shows variation and is influenced by storage conditions and the composition of the composites. The highest MC, 0.901%, is seen in composites devoid of fillers, likely due to free hydroxyl (-OH) groups in the resin and fibers that attract moisture. When

Table 3: Parameters for Physical characteristics and dimensional stability of developed hybrid polymer composites

Parameters	Physical Properties Test			
	Density	Moisture Content	Water Absorption	Thickness Swelling
ASTM Standards	ASTM D1895	ASTM D570	ASTM D570	ASTM D570
Sample Size (mm ³)	20X10x3	20X20X3	20X20X3	20X20X3
Formula Used	$Ma \times \rho_w / (Ma - Mw)$	$[(Mt_2 - Mt_1) / Mt_1] \times 100$	$[(Lt_2 - Lt_1) / Lt_1] \times 100$	$[(T_2 - T_1) / T_1] \times 100$
Remarks	Mw and Ma = mass (weight) of sample weighed in distilled water and air respectively, and ρ_w = density of distilled water .	Mt ₂ and Mt ₁ = The mass (weight) of the sample before and after drying in the oven respectively.	Lt ₁ and Lt ₂ = The mass (weight) of the specimen before and after water immersion respectively.	T ₁ and T ₂ = Thickness of the sample before and after water immersion respectively [31].

Figure 3: Specimens of developed composites for moisture, absorption and linear swelling test

fillers are added, MC decreases to 0.630%, suggesting a reduction in available hydroxyl groups. Fiber loading, particulate type, and surface exposure impact water absorption (WA) and swelling characteristics of these composites. The WA is at its peak (1.5%) without particulate fillers due to poor epoxy-fiber compatibility. Adding two

wt.% alumina/silicon carbide fillers reduce WA significantly; however, increasing the filler content from 2 to 6 wt.% causes a rise in WA and swelling dimensions—thickness, width, and length—due to the hydrophilic nature of aluminium oxide particulates, which exacerbate moisture uptake and affect the dimensional stability of the composites [26, 27].

Table 4: Physical properties and dimensional stability of developed composites for different periods

Physical Properties	Time (Hrs.)	Samples			
		P	Q	R	S
Density (gm/cm ³)		2.708	2.651	2.659	2.662
Moisture Content (%)	8	0.699	0.42	0.367	0.314
	16	0.901	0.672	0.646	0.63
	24	0.901	0.672	0.646	0.63
Water Absorption (%)	8	0.901	0.336	0.372	0.395
	16	1.197	0.504	0.646	0.711
	24	1.5	0.672	0.741	0.869
Thickness Swelling (%)	8	23.864	17.55	17.783	21.32
	16	25.142	19.163	19.79	21.458
	24	25.568	19.256	20.115	21.875
Width Swelling (%)	8	0.432	0.25	0.302	0.333
	16	0.592	0.482	0.538	0.565
	24	0.688	0.547	0.605	0.632
Length swelling (%)	8	0.579	0.264	0.33	0.334
	16	2.319	0.495	0.496	0.501
	24	2.421	0.56	0.596	0.602

Figure 4: Comparison of density, moisture, absorption and linear swelling of developed composites

5. Conclusions

The research comprehensively explores the impact of alumina and silicon carbide additives on the physical characteristics and dimensional stability of epoxy/glass fiber hybrid polymer composites.

- The study evaluates how the behaviour of epoxy/glass fiber hybrid polymer composites are affected by the addition of silicon carbide and alumina in a 1:1 ratio.
- Because of the best bonding between the epoxy and the glass fibers, filler-free composites are found to have the highest density (2.708 g/cm³), as well as the highest rate of water absorption (1.5 %) and thickness swelling (25.568 %) because of the poor material compatibility
- Introduction of 2 wt. % alumina/silicon carbide fillers initially decreases water absorption to 0.672% and reduces linear swelling across all dimensions, demonstrating the hydrophobic benefits of silicon carbide.
- However, increasing the filler content to 6 wt.% alumina/silicon carbide results in a rise in moisture content to 0.672%, water absorption to 0.869%, and enhances linear swelling (thickness swelling at 21.875%, width swelling at 0.632%, and length swelling at 0.602%), driven by the hydrophilic nature of aluminium oxide.

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- These findings highlight the critical role of filler content and type in balancing the mechanical strength and moisture resistance of epoxy/glass fiber composites.
- The study provides valuable insights for optimizing the design and utilization of polymer-based composites, suggesting that precise control of filler ratios can tailor properties for specific industrial needs, enhancing durability and moisture resistance.
- These materials could potentially benefit sectors where durability and dimensional stability under environmental stress are crucial, such as in automotive brake components.

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7. Declaration of competing interest

The authors certify that none of the research or conclusions reported in this publication could have been influenced by any personal or financial conflicts of interest.

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